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The role of interpersonal communication in promoting team morale: a case study of tech startups in Lagos, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study aimed to analyze the role of interpersonal communication in promoting team morale in the workplace. The sample ($N = 130$) was drawn from different levels within the organization and the research technique utilized was a comprehensive survey methodology. The survey explored the crucial outlook of interpersonal communication in the workplace including team morale, employee's performance, job satisfaction, and leadership style in promoting team morale. The exhaustive purpose of this study was to analyze how interpersonal communication affects team morale and employees performance in the workplace and to recommend other opportunities to improve communication dynamics in the workplace. The research findings revealed that interpersonal communication has a significant positive impact on team morale and employees performance in the workplace. However, impending challenges such as communication tools, initiatives, leadership style, and chain of command barriers pose a threat to communication improvement as well as employees morale in the workplace. This study necessitates organizations to prioritize effective communication training between team leaders and employees in the workplace.

Keywords: Interpersonal Communication; Organization; Workplace; Team Morale; Employees Performance.

1. Introduction

An organization is a collection of people whose activities are consciously designed, coordinated, and directed by their members in order to pursue explicit purposes and attain particular *common objectives* or *goals*. (McAulley and Friends, 2007). In every organization, transparent and effective communication enables employees to feel comfortable performing their duties while helping the organization actualize its organizational objectives. Workplace dynamics ensure employees effectively communicate with each other for project development and allow for team building through individual performance. The quality of communication among employees in the workplace plays an integral role in not only organizational development and growth but also in employees morale and performance appraisals.

In a contemporary business environment, the relationship between interpersonal communication and team morale has rapidly become important as organizations increasingly rely on effective communication to maintain productivity and team cohesion. Tech startups, especially in innovative and developing environments such as Lagos, Nigeria, present

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unique challenges due to their dynamic nature. While tech startups thrive on innovation, agility, and collaborative teamwork, they are often faced with challenges such as heightened pressures from tight deadlines, and competitive market conditions. This makes interpersonal communication essential for team members to succeed while maintaining high morale and efficiency.

An excellent employee morale is defined as the ambience, feelings of well-being, and job satisfaction derived from the positive work culture and environment in an organization. The result of positive employee morale fosters growth, overall organizational success in the organization and, thus, boosts employees performance. Employees' performance is the result of work performed by employees, and these results have a concrete relationship between the strategic goals of the organization, economic contribution, and customer satisfaction (Wibowo 2007:7). Employee performance helps determine the success of a company and its value in the competitive market. In order to maintain their competitive abilities, the company's interests prioritize their human resources, communication, and branding, as well as their overall management. Employee performance also plays a vital role in the achievement of the objectives of the company.

There are numerous factors that influence employees morale and performance in Tech Startups and a major determinant is interpersonal communication. Interpersonal communication is a process whereby information is exchanged along with understanding, which is an important factor in predicting the success of an organization (Lunenburg & Irby, 2006). As the Nigeria Tech Industry continues to boom at a rapid pace especially in Lagos, the constant demand for building excellent interpersonal communication skills increases. Tech Startups rely heavily on teamwork with interpersonal communication serving as the fundamentals of collaboration and innovation. The role of effective communication among team members in an organization is not to be underestimated, and different literature has established a significant relationship between interpersonal communication, employees performance, and team's morale. Meanwhile, leadership style, chain-in-command barriers, and communication tools exhibit different variations in effective communication in the workplace.

The objective of this research is to explore the role of interpersonal communication and how it increases employees performance, boosts team morale, and promotes a positive work culture in tech startups. By unraveling the different components of communication in the workplace, this study seeks to identify current challenges caused by the underestimation of interpersonal communication and ultimately offer various recommendations towards building and sustaining positive interpersonal communication in the organization. Through this research, organizations particularly tech startups would have an invaluable resource to improve their employees morale by using interpersonal communication as their communication strategies, job satisfaction, long-term success, and productivity in the workplace.

2. Elements of Interpersonal communication

Communicator: Communication is the continuous process of transmitting verbal and non-verbal information, ideas, thoughts, and emotions. Communication occurs every day using spoken words, symbols, signs, and non-verbal gestures. Communication involves two or more persons, and there is usually a sender and a receiver. The fundamental technique of communication starts when a single person chooses to formulate an idea (F. Fusi and F. Zhang 2020). An idea or message that must be conveyed using a channel to the receiver. It is important that the receiver comprehends the message intended by the sender in order to give feedback.

- **Sender:** A sender is the encoder in the communication process. In the process, the sender elicits the necessary reaction or symbol to communicate the message, which comes through any channel. The influence on the message being passed across is dependent on the sender's verbal and non-verbal ability. This ability also influences how the recipient will understand the message being passed along.
- **Receiver:** This is the recipient in whom the message was aimed. The receiver's feedback to the message is dependent on their level of comprehension of the information received.
- **Message:** This is the idea the receiver is sending across. It can come as a sign, symbol or speech and it is complete when the recipient gives feedback.
- **Channel:** This is the medium used to communicate. There must be an appropriate communication channel, and selecting the right channel is essential to the recipient's interpretation of the message. For instance, in a face-to-face conversation, voice and vision are used, but during a cellphone call, the route is limited to only speech (M. Chinakidzwa and M. Phiri 2020). An oral channel is selected when the receiver must provide immediate feedback, while a written channel is selected when the message needs to be delivered when the feedback is not necessarily urgent.

- **Feedback:** The communication process is not complete without feedback. Feedback is a message sent by the recipient to the sender, and it enables the sender to control, change, replay, or verify if the receiver correctly interpreted the message (A. Gutterman, 2021). Feedback can be written down in channels such as documents, reports, memos, banners, and printings. It can also be expressed verbally or nonverbally using facial expressions, signs, sighs, and other non-verbal cues.
- **Barriers:** Communication barriers are obstacles and challenges faced during the communication process. These barriers can include gestures, noises, and technical problems during the communication process.

2.1. Statement of Problem

Although many studies have been conducted on the role of interpersonal communication in facilitating organizational performance, its influence on team morale in tech startups particularly in Lagos, Nigeria remains underestimated. The unique challenges posed by startup environments, such as wanting to maximize profits and minimizing cost, high-pressure work schedules, and never changing market conditions, negatively affect employee morale if not properly managed. In Lagos, where the tech ecosystem is still emerging and developing at a fast pace, these challenges are even more pronounced. Tech startups in Lagos often operate with Agile teams, which heightens the need for seamless and effective communication. Yet, many of these Tech Startups face communication barriers that undermine team morale. Some of these barriers include, lack of clear communication channels, misalignment of goals, insufficient feedback mechanisms, favoritism, nepotism, and cultural or interpersonal differences among team members, these often leads to low employee productivity thereby leading to high retention rate and poor overall performance.

Moreover, the increasing reliance on digital communication tools, while necessary for remote or hybrid work arrangements, can sometimes create distance between team members, making it difficult to build the trust, collaboration and innovation required to maintain high morale. Without regular, meaningful interpersonal interactions such as team bonding activities, employee relation activities, constant feedback surveys, and incentives, team members may feel isolated or misunderstood, leading to a decline in collaboration and cooperation. Despite the rapid growth of the tech industry in Lagos, there is a notable gap in the understanding of how communication practices influence team dynamics and morale within this specific sector. Many tech startups focus more on innovation and product development and making profits than simplifying their people process and fostering healthy communication environments, often at the expense of employee well-being. If these issues are not addressed, startups risk reduction in creativity, decreasing productivity, and losing valuable talent to competitors.

This study seeks to address the existing gap by examining how interpersonal communication influences team morale in Lagos-based tech startups. It will explore the ways in which communication challenges manifest in this environment, as well as identify strategies for improving communication to enhance morale. Given the critical role that morale plays in employee retention, satisfaction, and overall team performance, understanding the connection between communication and morale is vital for the long-term sustainability of tech startups in Lagos.

2.2. Significance of Study

The role of interpersonal communication in promoting team morale within tech startups in Lagos, Nigeria, holds significant implications for multiple stakeholders, including investors, employees, human resources, and organizational leaders. The tech startup in Lagos is rapidly evolving, yet there are limited scholarly studies addressing the relationship between communication and morale. As startups face unique challenges, this study aims to address the knowledge gap by exploring how effective communication strategies can enhance team morale and improve overall organizational success.

2.2.1. Contribution to Organizational Success in Tech Startups

One of the primary contributions of this study is to provide actionable insights into how tech startups in Lagos can leverage interpersonal communication to boost employee morale and increase productivity. A motivated team is more likely to engage in creative problem-solving projects by taking ownership of projects, and working collaboratively towards shared goals. By identifying the types of communication that foster morale, whether through face-to-face interactions, digital tools, or leadership communication, this research offers practical recommendations for startups to cultivate a work environment that supports both employee well-being and organizational growth.

2.2.2. Addressing the Communication Challenges in Nigerian Startups

The tech ecosystem in Lagos is also marked by specific challenges like diversity and inclusion, and limited access to advanced management frameworks. Many startups operate with small teams that often lack formalized communication protocols. This can lead to frequent misunderstandings, unclear roles, and conflicts that erode team morale over time.

This research on Lagos Tech startups allows for analysis of these challenges by exploring specific barriers to effective communication and proposing impactful solutions.

2.2.3. Enhancing Leadership Practices

This study will have particular significance for leadership within tech startups, as it explores how leaders can influence team morale through effective communication. Leadership communication plays a pivotal role in shaping team dynamics, guiding vision, and fostering a supportive work culture. For leaders in tech startups, where hierarchies tend to be flat and leadership is often informal, mastering interpersonal communication is essential to maintaining high morale.

2.2.4. Implications for Human Resource Management

This research also holds value for human resource professionals within tech startups, particularly in developing employee engagement and retention strategies. High morale is directly linked to employee satisfaction, retention, and performance, all of which are crucial for startups that cannot afford high turnover or underperformance. Through this research, human resources professionals can gain a deeper understanding of the role of communication in promoting morale and well-being, helping them implement communication training, feedback systems, and conflict resolution mechanisms tailored to the startup environment. As tech startups continue to grow in Lagos, human resources professionals will need robust strategies to foster positive communication and morale in an increasingly competitive and stressful market.

2.2.5. Promoting Employee Well-Being

This research also places its focus on the importance of employee well-being. In tech startups, which often operate under high pressure and with long working hours, maintaining morale is essential for preventing burnout and ensuring sustainable productivity. By examining how communication can be used to create a supportive and inclusive work environment, this study highlights the importance of employee well-being as a key factor in startup success. Startups that prioritize communication and morale are more likely to retain top talent, reduce workplace stress, and build stronger, more resilient teams. The findings of this research will therefore be crucial for tech startups looking to create a more positive, healthy work culture.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Interpersonal Communication and Team Morale

According to Robbins and Judge (2013), their research suggests that effective interpersonal communication is closely linked to job satisfaction and morale. This is particularly true for tech startups, where innovation and collaboration are vital to success. When the structure of the organization fosters open communication between line managers and employees, team members can communicate openly and efficiently, therefore helping each other to grow, share ideas, and provide mutual support, which, in turn, leads to higher morale.

An organization that fosters open communication, provide supports to its employee and pay wages accordingly is more likely to be regarded as a great place to work compared to organizations whereby employees are compensated poorly, there is no transparency, limited growth, promotion is based on favoritism, hostile and toxic work environment and high turnover rate.

Monga, Verma, and Monga (2015), in their research paper “*Job Satisfaction of employees of ICICI Bank in Himachal Pradesh*”, analyzed employees satisfaction and how other organizational factors influence their job satisfaction in six different branches in Himachal Pradesh with over 80 employees. Organizational context and job satisfaction in the evidence of research found from their analysis of data revealed that various dimensions of organization including interpersonal relationship (70%), training and development (41.25%), salary (50%), work-life balance (48.75%), attitude of superior (67.5%), and morale (38.75%) among others, influence the morale of employees and their level of job satisfaction.

3.2. Role of Leadership in Interpersonal Communication

Leaders and their leadership style plays a significant role in setting the tone for communication within teams. Their communication style, whether open, transparent, and authoritarian can have a profound impact on team dynamics and morale. Leaders who foster open communication with adequate work transparency by actively listening to their

employees and team members are more likely to cultivate a positive work culture and sustainable work environment where employee morale is high.

According to Yukl (2012), transformational leadership characterized by vision, inspiration, and effective communication has been shown to positively impact team morale. Furthermore, Farid (2014), in his research study *“The Influence of Work Rotation, Interpersonal Communication, and Leadership Style on Work Motivation and Its Impact on Work Performance of Bapedal Aceh Employees”* explains the impact of leadership style on work performance and the morale of employees in the workplace. Through an effective leadership style and interpersonal communication in an organization, the skills of employees can be fully utilized i.e., an effective interpersonal communication in the organization enables a higher morale of employees attitude to work. Leadership style is a way to show attitude with the aim of influencing employees to achieve company goals (Handayani & Khairi, 2022).

Grace Akpougu (2022) analyzed morale-boosting strategies in her work, *“Assessment of Moral Boosting Strategies of employees in the Nigerian Manufacturing Industry.”* The ability of leaders and team leads to communicate frequently, engage employees in employee activities that would boost their morale, constantly increase their focus on employees training and development, and foster higher motivation and job satisfaction of employees in the workplace.

3.3. Theoretical Framework

3.3.1. Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory

Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory differentiates between hygiene factors and motivators. Hygiene factors such as salary, working conditions, and company policies prevent dissatisfaction but do not necessarily lead to satisfaction. Motivators such as compensation, recognition, responsibility, and opportunities for personal growth are intrinsic factors that drive satisfaction and morale.

Shaban et al. (2017:3) posited that the organizational approach that results in low staff morale is founded upon the level of respect that employees receive from the organization in which they work. Interpersonal communication can be seen as both a hygiene factor. Lack of respect for employees’ privacy, time and knowledge, poor communication, misunderstandings, or lack of feedback can contribute to dissatisfaction in the work environment leading to low morale and poor job performance. However, effective and open communication, important recognition, and positive interpersonal interactions can serve as motivators, boosting morale and increasing employee performance.

Low morale from employees are often caused by leadership styles where leaders micromanage their employees. Leaders influence morale as they interact with subordinates, leaders that allow for communication gaps reduce employee morale and workforce motivation by not making important business decisions such as frequent employee feedback, compensation and benefit, reviewing stringent company policies (Mallik *et al.* 2019).

3.3.2. Leadership Theories

In tech startups, especially in fast-paced environments like Lagos, the nature of leadership can greatly influence team morale and the effectiveness of communication. Leaders must adapt their communication styles to foster positive leader-member exchanges.

- **Transformational Leadership:** This is a leadership style that fosters, inspires and motivates their employees by creating a shared vision, fostering a sense of purpose, and encouraging personal and professional development. They also build strong emotional connections with their employees, which results in high levels of trust and engagement. Sundar Pichai, CEO of Google leadership style transformational approach creates high-quality exchanges where employees feel valued and supported. This leads to increased team morale, as employees feel inspired and trusted to take ownership of their work.
- **Transactional Leadership:** The transactional leadership style is more task-oriented and focuses on exchanges of rewards or punishments based on performance. While the transactional type of leadership style is not necessarily fostering the highest-quality exchanges, transactional leadership can still result in moderately effective relationships, particularly in organizations and roles where tasks are more structured, and immediate results are highly emphasized. Transactional leaders use formal exchanges, such as bonuses, raises, or recognition for completed tasks, to motivate employees. Adopting this type of leadership style can be less effective for organizations with low finances and management.
- **Autocratic Leadership:** This is a top-down approach where the leader makes decisions unilaterally without much input from team members. This style can result in low-quality morale, as employees may feel disconnected from the decision-making process and undervalued. While autocratic leadership can be effective

in crisis situations or where quick decisions are required, it often results in low morale over the long term. In Lagos-based tech startups, adopting an autocratic leadership style could hinder morale, particularly in creative industries where employee input and innovation are essential.

Therefore, leaders who prioritize transparent and empathetic communication with relevant solutions can positively influence employee engagement and morale. Leaders who provide regular feedback, recognize achievements, and create opportunities for open dialogue contribute to a culture of trust and mutual respect, which in turn enhances team morale (Avolio & Bass, 1995).

4. Methodology

4.1. Research Design

The data for this research was analyzed using primary and secondary sources of data collection. The primary source of data was mainly through the use of a semi-structured questionnaire, which was designed to elicit information on the role of interpersonal communication in promoting employees morale in the workplace. The secondary sources of data collections were sourced through journals and scholarly materials.

4.2. Research Methodology

This research will employ a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and quantitative research to explore the relationship between interpersonal communication and team morale. Quantitative data would be derived from 130 employees in different tech startups while qualitative data would be derived from different scholarly articles, journals and research.

4.3. Sample Size

A total of 130 employees participated in this study: 50% were men, 48.5% were women, and 1.5% preferred not to say, aged between 18 and 29 years (76.9%), aged between 30 and 39 (16.9%), aged between 40 and 49 years (3.8%) and between 50 and 59 (2.3%). The marital status of participants was, single (79.2%), married (16.2%), divorced (3.1%), and widowed (1.5%).

5. Data Presentation and Analysis of Data

A semi-structured survey was created based on the objectives of this research and was filled out by employees in different corporate organizations. The survey contained questions about socio-demographic variables (*gender, age, marital status, professional position, and level of academic qualifications*). The questions were formulated on a Likert-type scale from 1 to 5 (1=*strongly agree*; 2=*agree*; 3=*undecided*; 4=*disagree*; 5=*strongly disagree*).

5.1. Analysis of respondent Demographic Informations

Table 1 Gender Distribution of Respondents

Gender			
		Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	65	50
	Female	63	48.5
	Prefer not to say	2	1.5
	Total	130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

From the field survey table above, respondents' information analyzed according to their gender revealed that 50% of the respondents were males and 48.5% were females. This implies that the majority of the respondents were male.

Table 2 Age Distribution of Respondents

Age			
		Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-29 yrs	100	76.9
	30-39 yrs	22	16.9
	40-49 yrs	5	3.8
	50-59 yrs	3	2.3
Total		130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

From the table above, it is seen that 76.9% of the respondents were within the age group of 18 and 29 years, followed by those in the age group of 30 and 39 years at 16.9%, and those between the ages of 40 and 49 years at 3.8%. Moreover, those within the age group 50 and 59 years were represented at 2.3%.

Table 3 Marital Status of Respondents

Marital status			
		Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Married	21	16.2
	Single	103	79.2
	Widowed	2	1.5
	Divorced	4	3.1
	Total	130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

From the table above, respondent information was analyzed according to their marital status. Therefore, 16.2% of the respondents were married, while 79.2% were single. This implies that the majority of the respondents were single. Moreover, those divorced were represented at 3.1% and 1.5% of widowed.

Table 4 Respondents Professional Positions

Professional Position			
		Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Entry Level	76	58.5
	Mid Level	38	29.2
	Senior Executives	16	12.3
Total		130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

The above table shows that 58.5% of the respondents were entry-level, 29.2% of the respondents were mid-level employees, and 12.3% of the respondents were senior executives.

Table 5 Educational Level of Respondents

Level of Education			
		Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Valid	OND /HND	37	28.5
	BSC	77	59.2
	Masters	11	8.5
	PhD	5	3.8
Total		130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

The field survey table shows that 28.5% of the respondents were OND and HND holders, BSC settled at 59.2%, Masters respondents were 8.5%, and 3.8% of the respondents were PhD holders.

5.2. Psychographic Data Analysis

Table 6 Relationship Between Line Managers and Employees Based on Interpersonal Communication

Line managers and employees' relationship is based on their interpersonal communication.			
		Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	53	40.8
	Agree	23	17.7
	Undecided	14	10.8
	Disagree	20	15.4
	Strongly Disagree	20	15.4
	Total	130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

The responses obtained from the analysis of the respondents views on the statement above revealed that 53 (40.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed with the above question, 23 (17.7%) agreed with the statement, 14 (10.8%) of the respondents were undecided. Also, 53 (15.4%) of the respondents both disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. This establishes the objectives that line managers' roles and communication skills affect the job performance of employees in an organization.

Table 7 Influence of Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction

Leadership style poses a barrier to employee job satisfaction.			
		Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	25	19.2
	Agree	58	44.6
	Undecided	30	23.1
	Disagree	13	10
	Strongly Disagree	4	3.1
	Total	130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

The responses obtained from the analysis of the respondents' views on the statement above showed that 25 (19.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed with the above question, 58 (44.6%) agreed with the statement, and 17 (13.1%) of the respondents were undecided. Also, 38 (29.2%) disagreed and 19(14.6%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement. Leadership styles and chains of command in an organization can pose a threat to employee job satisfaction, especially in organizations where their organograms are taken seriously. From this analysis, it appears that leadership styles can prevent employees from maximizing their talents, thus affecting their job performance.

Table 8 Importance of Prioritizing Employee Welfare for Promoting Interpersonal Communication

To promote interpersonal communication, organizations should prioritize employee welfare.			
		Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	53	40.8
	Agree	27	20.8
	Undecided	17	13.1
	Disagree	15	11.5
	Strongly Disagree	18	13.8
	Total	130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

The responses obtained from the analysis of the respondents views on the statement above showed that 53 (40.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed with the above question, 18 (20.8%) agreed with the statement, and 17 (13.1%) of the respondents were undecided. Also, 15 (11.5%) disagreed and 18 (13.8%) strongly disagreed with the statement. Employees welfare can be beneficial to employees depending on the initiatives. Few organizations create employee welfare initiatives but do not handle the cost and management. However, 40.8% agreed that creating welfare schemes for employees promotes interpersonal communication.

Table 9 The Role of Effective Communication from Leaders in Promoting Organizational Growth

Effective communication from leaders helps promote organizational growth and boost employees morale.			
		Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	23	17.7
	Agree	69	53.1
	Undecided	23	17.7
	Disagree	8	6.2
	Strongly Disagree	7	5.4
	Total	130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

The responses obtained from the analysis of the respondents views on the statement above showed that 23 (17.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed with the above question, 69(53.1%) agreed with the statement, 23 (17.7%) of the respondents were undecided. Also, 8 (6.2%) disagreed and 7 (5.4%) strongly disagreed with the statement. Clear, concise, and transparent communication helps employees to feel welcomed in the workplace. Therefore, it can be deduced that effective interpersonal communication in the workplace promotes organizational goals and boosts employee morale.

Table 10 Impact of Inadequate Communication Tools and Unnecessary Chain of Command on Employee Performance

Employees' overall performance can be influenced by inadequate communication tools and an unnecessary chain of command.			
		Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	19	14.6
	Agree	40	30.8
	Undecided	36	27.7
	Disagree	27	20.8
	Strongly Disagree	8	6.2
	Total	130	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

The responses obtained from the analysis of the respondents views on the statement above showed that 19 (14.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed with the above question, 40 (30.8%) agreed with the statement, and 36 (27.7%) of the respondents were undecided. Also, 27 (20.8%) disagreed, and 8 (6.2%) strongly disagreed with the statement. Unnecessary chains of command and poor communication techniques such as gossiping, a lack of sincerity, discrepancies between what was communicated and what was understood can affect employee overall job performance.

6. Discussion of Findings

The main objective of this research was to explore how interpersonal communication promotes employee morale in Tech startups in Lagos, Nigeria. The analysis from the data provided indicates the positive significance and overall importance of the role of interpersonal communication in employee job satisfaction, morale, and performance. Through this research, it has been deduced that interpersonal communication among employees is an invaluable asset in Tech Startups. Leadership style and interpersonal communication among team leads in Tech startups are variables that affect employee performance in the workplace.

The survey result further proved that leadership and communication tools are positively correlated with employee morale. This is because the support given by a team leads to their team members can affect their performance and, thus, the overall performance of the organization.

7. Conclusion

It is concluded that there is an association between employee morale, leadership style, and interpersonal communication in the workplace. The survey results and responses from employees explain the role of training and development. It is important to continually train employees and leaders in the workplace on the importance of interpersonal communication and how it affects not only employee morale but also organizational objectives.

Recommendations

This research revealed the importance and influence of interpersonal communication in promoting employee morale in Tech startups in Lagos, Nigeria. Based on the survey results and discussion of the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to help Tech startups increase the development of effective interpersonal communication in their organization.

- **Training and Development:** Organizations must increase the intensity of interpersonal communication in the workplace through constant training and development curricula structured on communication with practical instances. This constant training can improve the relationship between employees and their team leads, thus promoting organizational objectives.
- **Leadership Style:** Freedom to converse with leaders despite the company's organizational structure can further boost employee morale in the workplace. For instance, if the relationship between an employee and their team lead appears to be toxic, there should be room for the employee to speak with a leader who is not directly responsible for the employee. A chain of command can exist, however, employees must be prioritized

when creating the chain of command. Leadership style is also a cogent factor in promoting employee morale in the workplace, and good leadership skills will motivate employee morale and boost their enthusiasm towards their job performance.

- **Employees Welfare:** An organization becomes a great place to work when they prioritize their employees welfare and provide schemes or opportunities for employee's growth. Welfare programmes must be fully funded by the organization as this helps to motivate employees in the workplace.
- **Feedback Channels:** There should be channels for feedback to the management. Whistleblowing, anonymous feedback, Google forms, feedback form, quarterly or annual feedback surveys are channels that can be created for effective feedback from the employee to the management or their team leads.

In conclusion, it is highly recommended that companies prioritize providing motivating factors, effective and open communication, as well as feedback mechanisms in the workplace.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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